

THE HARMONY OF POSITIVISM AND ROMANTICISM IN SHAROF RASHIDOV'S "SONG OF KASHMIR"

Kh.M. Radjapboyeva

Independent researcher of the Department of Social and Humanitarian Studies, Andijan State
Medical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15876374>

Abstract. *This article analyzes the artistic and aesthetic directions in Sharof Rashidov's "Song of Kashmir". The literary and philosophical essence of the harmony of the positivist approach and romantic images observed in the work is revealed. The high aesthetic level of the work is based on the synthesis of realistic images based on scientific facts and romantic melodies expressing dreams and feelings by the author.*

Keywords: *Sharof Rashidov, Song of Kashmir, positivism, romanticism, aesthetic harmony, realistic image, dreams, artistic thinking.*

Introduction

Today, the development of the science of aesthetics and aesthetic principles in the world is being studied as a complex and multifaceted phenomenon within the framework of extensive scientific research. In particular, aesthetic analysis is not limited to the creator, the work of art and its recipient, but is carried out inextricably with the development trends of artistic culture, creative processes and the aesthetic needs of society. In scientific research in this regard, the artistic and literary heritage of Sharof Rashidov, especially his work "Song of Kashmir", is receiving special attention. The aesthetic concepts and means of artistic expression in this work serve as an important source for the formation of new views, methods of interpretation and scientific approaches in art criticism and literary criticism. Sharof Rashidov is one of the creators who combined the artistic and journalistic style in Uzbek literature. His work "Song of Kashmir" is based on his impressions from a trip to India, in which not only observation, but also inspiration, love and aesthetic images play a key role. This article scientifically analyzes the harmony of the positivism and romanticism movements manifested in the work.

Literature review

The life path of Sh. Rashidov, his activities as a state and public figure, his political portrait, his role in Uzbekistan's international relations, his contribution to the socio-economic and cultural development of the country, and in some cases his artistic creativity, have been analyzed in a number of scientific works published by historians Iskandarov I, Rizayev S, Rashidov A, Rashidova G. Sh, Abdusamadov F, Muzaffarov A, Alimardonov T, Ergashev Sh, Numonzoda S, Kurbanova Sh.D, Xasanova Glar. Foreign studies also recognize the important role played by Sharof Rashidov in the development of Uzbekistan, and consider his activities as the first secretary of the Communist Party of Uzbekistan, a candidate for membership in the Politburo of the CPSU Central Committee in 1961-1983, as well as his views as one of the political leaders who played an important role in Soviet foreign policy.

The studies conducted by literary scholars Mirazizova R, Eshimov F, Mukhamedova G. I, Khodzhimetova D.D, Rashidova Sh. R, Bozorov E, Jamol Kamol, Ergashev Sh, Pardayeva D. R, Fayzulayev B focus on such aspects as the language and style of Sharof Rashidov's works, the

reflection of nationality and internationalism in them, the writer's creative path, and his literary and critical views. Also, Sh. Based on Rashidov's works, research has been conducted on the spiritual and moral education of future teachers. At the same time, literary works have also been created, which mainly include memoirs about Sh. Rashidov, descriptions of events related to the writer's life, and excerpts from literary works dedicated to him.

The scientific studies of G. T. Makhmudova and O. J. Uroкова analyze aspects of Sharof Rashidov's personality, his phenomenon, philosophical and aesthetic interpretation of the writer's literary heritage, and poetic thinking. The studies of K. S. Mahmudov focus on Sh. Rashidov's political leadership and its contradictory features in conditions of totalitarianism, the role of international culture and national leadership in Sh. Rashidov's leadership style, as well as Sh. Rashidov's leadership role in conditions of colonialism.

Research Methodology. The article uses the methods of interdisciplinary approach (literature and philosophy), objectivity, historicism and logic, typological analysis, comparative analysis.

Analysis and results. In the work, positivist views are expressed through a clear depiction of real events, facts, socio-political situations. Romanticism is reflected through the depiction of nature, the qualities of the people, inspiration and ideals. Rashidov enriched his observations not only in a journalistic form, but also with poetic, emotionally rich images. The two trends in "Kashmir Song" - positivism and romanticism - complement each other. Positivism is the main support of the work, the author relies on facts, analyzes real life.

Literature is a reflection of human thinking. Various aesthetic trends play an important role in its development. Sharof Rashidov, a prominent figure of 20th-century Uzbek literature, in his "Kashmir Song" a created a unique artistic space by combining the currents of positivism and romanticism in the work. This article analyzes the expression of these two currents in the work, their harmony and aesthetic impact.

Positivism - scientifically based realism. Positivism is an approach based on understanding reality through observation, experience and scientific thinking. In the work "Song of Kashmir", Rashidov describes the socio-political life, historical development and natural environment of the Indian people in a clear, documentary style.

- Geographical, cultural and historical reality: The work describes the geographical location of Kashmir, climate, natural resources, and customs of the people based on facts. He studied the nature, population, culture and historical events of the region and reflected them in an artistic form.

- **Analysis of social problems:** The author was able to reveal social inequality, interethnic conflicts, and the consequences of colonialism in the life of the Indian people in a rational approach.

- Observation and contemplation: The details in the work are enriched by Rashidov's personal journey, observations and journalistic experience.

Romanticism - a combination of inspiration and feelings. Romanticism is expressed in the work through the desire, passion and need of the human soul to search for beauty:

- Fascination with the beauty of Kashmir: Natural landscapes - mountains, valleys, flowers - are given not only as images, but also as artistic symbols. They are a source of desire, tranquility and inspiration.

- The world of ideals: Rashidov expresses common ideals such as peace, friendship of peoples, goodness and human love through Kashmir. This is the main essence of romanticism.

- Poetic expression: Despite being prose, the language of the work is strong in musicality, melody, and poetics in images. This is a product of artistic inspiration.

Aesthetic harmony - the unity of rational and emotional approaches. The power of the work lies precisely in the harmony of two trends - positivism and romanticism. The following table shows this harmony:

Positivist approach Romantic approach Harmony.

Accurate observations, facts Symbols, feelings beautiful interpretation of reality.

Socio-political understanding Dreams and inspiration

Aesthetic approach to real life. Thought-based style Emotional experiences.

Harmony of mind and heart. Let us pay attention to these attractive sentences in the work "Song of Kashmir": "In the Garden of Flowers, which embodied all the beauties of nature and added beauty to the beauty of the blue-green valley, the music of love and life triumphed. The melodies that gave peace to the hearts sometimes accompanied the sweet voices of girls, sometimes the dancing of the nightingales, intoxicated by the play of flowers, sometimes the charming melodies that were blown by the flutes of shepherds in the lap of the mountains." The author uses Kashmir as a metaphor in this work through the ideas of the beauty of nature, its impact on human emotions and the search for peace. The charm of Kashmir and the aesthetic power it embodies are shown in the work as being related to the spiritual state and inner world of a person.

This in a unique way expresses the harmony of nature and the spiritual state of a person. The unique melody of flowers, the joyful play of Nargiz, Violet, Tulip, Rose, describes how pleasant it is to enjoy and enjoy a peaceful, calm life. While reading the work "Song of Kashmir", we encounter mythical images. The king of bees, Bambur, the queen of flowers "Nargiz" are the embodiment of positive characters, while the opposite characters, the Storm, the pest Harut, are embodied in the form of negative characters.

Through the author's unique creative skills and boundless artistic thinking, Bambur and Nargiz are surrounded by trees, fragrant scents, heart ties, birds, and flowers, protecting them in any situation and depicting them in a benevolent manner. In the footsteps of the negative characters, Boron and Horut, dark images such as wind, plague, scythe, and lightning are interpreted. Sharof Rashidov, while wielding his pen in the vastness of high artistic thinking, was able to convey the revival of mother nature, its entry into language like humans, and its life-giving activity, consisting of the struggle for eternal and eternal existence, in the form of symbolic images with unparalleled skill. The originality, richness, and diversity of the language and style of the work, the uniqueness of the author's style of depiction, the richness of metaphors, adjectives, and similes can attract every reader and literary critics.

Conclusion and recommendations. Sharof Rashidov's philosophical and aesthetic views are relevant to the role of aesthetic categories in the history of Uzbek literature in expressing the national, social, universal and moral content and essence, as well as in the formation of human attitudes and imagination in the works of the writer. It is significant in that it is a source of noble ideas that serve as a source of inspiration. The socio-philosophical essence of the artistic and aesthetic images in Sharof Rashidov's "Song of Kashmir" is based on national and universal values, and effective spiritual and educational mechanisms for using them to improve the national education system have been developed. Sharof Rashidov's "Song of Kashmir" is valued as an example of a new aesthetic harmony in Uzbek literature. The author not only observed reality, but also saw it with the eyes of the soul. The harmony of positivist thinking and romantic inspiration in the work brought it to a high level both scientifically and artistically. Through this harmony, Rashidov not only illuminated the beauty of Kashmir, but also the noble aspirations of the human

heart. In the educational process, based on the artistic and aesthetic analysis of the work, it is necessary to include such topics as "Nature and Man in Sharof Rashidov's Poetry" and "Philosophy of Being in Uzbek Literature" in the curriculum; To enhance the aesthetic taste of the younger generation by creating online literary-analytical videos and podcasts based on the work "Song of Kashmir"; Based on the "museum pedagogy" column, it would be appropriate to organize sections such as "Kashmir Song - a symbol of love and the Motherland", "Rashidov and literature" in the exhibition halls of the "Age of Sharof Rashidov"; it would be advisable to prepare series of programs such as "Sharof Rashidov's Life and Heritage", "History of Kashmir Song", "In the Memory of Contemporaries" in cooperation with the "History of Uzbekistan" TV channel.

REFERENCES

1. Rashidov, Sh. Kashmir Song. – Tashkent: Gafur Ghulom Publishing House of Literature and Art, 1981.
2. Nazarov, Q. Introduction to Literary Studies. – Tashkent: Teacher, 2005.
3. Ganiev, B. Aesthetic Views and Literary Currents. – Samarkand: Zarafshon, 2018.
4. Karimov, A. Sharof Rashidov's life and work. – Tashkent: Ma'naviyat, 2022.
5. Ta'limov, S. "On the harmony of positivism and romanticism". // Literary studies, 2019, No. 3.
6. Sharof Rashidov. Kashmir song. Tashkent, Young Guard, 1978.